

The Impact of the Emerging Turanian Factor on International Relations

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Abstract: This article discusses the formation of the Turon Union by Turkic-speaking countries and the significance of this union in international relations. It explores how the emerging Turon factor, expected to form as a union, will influence the political activity of key international actors such as the United States, China, and Russia. Specifically, the article examines the process of these Turkic nations forming an economic, political, or military alliance, considering the factors highlighted by political analysts and the extent to which external political threats might impact the union's formation. The future role of the emerging Turon factor in political processes is analyzed in detail. Additionally, the internal political dynamics of the member states, their mutual political cooperation, and their relations within the framework of the union are also highlighted. The views of the people of the member countries on the establishment of this union are thoroughly explained. This article is recommended for specialists and independent researchers in the fields of international relations, political science, and military studies.

Keywords: Turon factor, Central Asia region, Turkey, Organization of Turkic States, Security dilemma.

In recent times, the essence of the Turon Union, which has become one of the pressing issues in the international political arena, must be addressed, particularly regarding what situation will prevail in global politics if this union indeed comes into existence in the future. First and foremost, to what extent does the Turon factor hold significant importance in international politics? The foundation of the Turon Union, expected to be established on the basis of the Organization of Turkic States formed in 2009, will undoubtedly be composed of Turkic countries. However, the geographic location of these countries is also crucial for the future of the union. Most Turkic countries are located in Central Asia, with only Azerbaijan and Turkey situated in the Southwest Asia region.

Following their independence from the Soviet Union in the 1990s, several ethnic and religious conflicts occurred among the countries in the region, particularly Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan. The primary reason for this situation is the "national-territorial delimitation" policy pursued by the Soviet Union in the early 1920s. This policy was based on the principle of "divide and rule." Consequently, as a result of the misguided and ruthless policies implemented, territorial disputes and conflicts arose among the newly independent countries. Even today, territorial disputes have not been completely resolved. A major issue complicating these territorial disputes is the problem of "enclave territories." These disputed areas exist in each of the Turkic countries in the Central Asia region. The Organization of

Turkic States was established in 2009 in the city of Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan, through the initiative and efforts of Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Azerbaijan. However, Uzbekistan did not express a desire to join this organization at that time. This was because the country had encountered several political disagreements with its neighboring countries, namely Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkey. Additionally, Uzbekistan's aspiration to lead among the Turkic countries hindered its path to membership. However, Uzbekistan lacked sufficient power and strength for leadership, as it had just gained independence from the Soviet Union. The country's economic, political, and military capabilities were at a low level, and its governance system was not fully equipped for independent functioning. Despite these shortcomings and unresolved issues, the country still desired to maintain leadership in its hands. This situation can be assessed as follows: Uzbekistan is recognized by Turkic countries as the historical homeland of all Turkic nations. Another problematic aspect for Uzbekistan's leadership is Turkey's pan-Turkism ideology and claims to expand over the territories of the former Ottoman Empire, which may indicate that Uzbekistan might not be able to assume a leading role.

Currently, Turkey is considered a country with high economic and military potential, not only among Turkic nations but globally. Despite being a member of NATO, Turkey possesses the capability for active independent military operations in the Middle East. However, recent incorrect economic reforms by the Turkish government have led the country into a state of economic crisis. In the 2023 presidential election, Erdoğan again secured victory. After accepting the presidential mandate and announcing the new government's composition, he stated that he would completely eliminate the economic issues facing the country. However, even a year after the elections, no significant progress has been made.

As for the other members of the Turkic states, Kazakhstan has emerged as a leading country in Central Asia in recent years from a military-economic perspective. According to the "Global Fire Power Ranking" report, Kazakhstan is recognized as a country with a strong army, surpassing Uzbekistan in military capability. Economically, Kazakhstan is the second-largest economy among the member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). For this reason, Kazakhstan's efforts to take a leadership role in the Turkic world have intensified recently. Since the establishment of the Organization of Turkic States, Kazakhstan has actively sought to engage with other Turkic countries, especially fostering significant economic and political relations with Turkey. For instance, during the official visit of Turkish Prime Minister Recep Tayyip Erdoğan to Kazakhstan in May 2012, a joint economic program called "New Synergy" was confirmed with then-Kazakh President Nursultan Nazarbayev. This program aimed to create favorable conditions for developing trade relations between the Customs Union countries and Turkey.

In essence, this situation indicates Turkey's de facto role as a bridge connecting integration structures among Turkic countries in Central Asia. Bilateral trade began at \$30 million in 1992 and reached \$3.1266 billion by the end of 2019, with \$2.8165 billion recorded in the first eleven months of 2020. Over the last five years, the volume of external trade between Kazakhstan and Turkey has increased by one and a half times, with Kazakhstan's share rising from 2.7% to 3.6%. Due to Kazakhstan's economic policies, the negative trade outcomes with partners in the European Union and CIS differ significantly, as trade with Russia and Belarus has decreased, while the trade balance with Turkey consistently favors Kazakhstan. In the first eleven months of 2018, mutual trade between Turkey and Kazakhstan reached \$1.1214 billion, increasing to \$1.4884 billion in 2019. For comparison, the positive trade balance between Kazakhstan and Turkey was \$535.3 million in 2015. From 2015 to 2019, Kazakhstan's exports to Turkey increased by 1.8 times to \$2.3075 billion, primarily through the supply of oil, copper, wheat, aluminum, zinc, and other raw materials. In contrast, imports from Turkey grew at a lower rate of 10.5%, reaching \$819.1 million. The products imported

from Turkey mainly include clothing, textiles, furniture, electrical appliances, automobiles, and other items. Furthermore, both countries organically complement each other in bilateral trade, meaning they do not compete in third-party markets. Additionally, during the COVID-19 pandemic, Kazakhstan became one of the primary tourist destinations for Turkey due to the well-developed air travel system between the two countries. Turkey has invested more than \$4 billion in Kazakhstan's economy since its independence.¹

The Kazakhstan-Turkey relationship has elevated not only in economic aspects but also politically. Not only are the relations between Turkey and Kazakhstan developing positively, but relations with other Turkic countries have also recently reached new levels in military and economic-political fields. Regarding Turkey's membership in NATO, it did not abandon its ideological beliefs and views despite being part of the organization. Instead, Turkey was able to spread its ideology across the Turkic-Muslim world. After World War II, Turkey needed military strength to counter the communist ideology led by the USSR, and NATO served as a source of this military power for Turkey. After joining NATO, pan-Turkism ideologies gained relevance as ideological tools against the USSR, aimed at separating the Central Asian and Azerbaijani republics from the Soviet Union. The collapse of the USSR in 1991 created conditions for the restoration of the pan-Turkic movement. New sovereign independent Turkic states emerged in the former Soviet territory, including Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. Turkey viewed them as "little brothers." Moreover, Turkey actively engaged as an initiator of cultural, humanitarian, and scientific projects within Russia. In the early 1990s, the Assembly of Turkic Peoples was established in Kazan, marking a significant event in the history of pan-Turkism, as it represented an organized phase of its development.

The idea of pan-Turkism has received negative political reactions from all countries surrounding the Turkic world. There are numerous Turkic minorities in Russia, China, Iran, Bulgaria, Greece, Georgia, and Afghanistan. For Armenia, any action towards the unity of Turks is perceived as a threat to its territorial integrity. Additionally, there is concern in many Western countries due to historically biased views and approaches toward Turks. Nevertheless, this situation does not negate the existence of a strategy to control "Eurasian Heartland" through "Great Turan." Considering all these factors, pan-Turkism is gradually evolving without achieving any concrete political results so far. Initially, Turkey aims to achieve ideological unification among Turkic nations through strengthening cultural, social, and economic ties. The first phase of the pan-Turkism strategy is progressing successfully, with economic and cultural cooperation already established among Turkic countries. Given recent relations, Ankara is in the process of transitioning to the second phase. The primary goal in this phase is to unite six independent Turkic countries as a political alliance. Independent Turkic states stand to gain significantly from the pan-Turkic project. Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Kazakhstan are directly interested in promoting the "Great Turan" idea and are working to establish new organizations, forums, and associations. The Turkish ethno-linguistic unity aligns with a promising trade route from Asia to Europe and provides access from the "Rimland" to the "Heartland." "Pan-Turkism" and "Neo-Ottomanism" are the pillars of Turkey's "Soft Power" strategy, which has intensified Ankara's desire to become a regional leader by changing its behavioral strategies. The first inactive phase is associated with Turgut Özal and Süleyman Demirel. This phase began during the presidency of Turgut Özal in Turkey. The turning point in the relations between the countries of South Caucasus and the Republic of Turkey during the first phase was the policy of Turkish President Turgut Özal

¹ Казахстан и магия Великого Турана - Ведомости Казахстана <https://kazvedomosti.kz/article/kazakhstan-i-magiya-velikogo-turana/>

(1989-1993), who began to pursue an active foreign policy from a position of “soft power” in the region.

In the second active phase of strategy implementation, the turning point in the relations between the countries of South Caucasus, Central Asia, and the Russian Federation and the Republic of Turkey is marked by the political movement of Turkish President Süleyman Demirel, which qualitatively strengthened the foreign policy towards the former Soviet countries and the Turkic world.

The third phase of Turkey's foreign policy "soft power" is characterized by Ahmet Davutoglu's policies, whose doctrine of "zero problems with neighbors" and "three methodological principles and five action principles" is seen as an active political principle aimed at uniting Turkic countries. The third phase is currently actively implemented by Turkey's President Recep Tayyip Erdoğan and former Foreign Minister Mevlüt Çavuşoğlu, who have achieved certain successes by combining "soft" power with real strength in the region and expanded Turkey's geopolitical influence areas.

“The last century has turned into a page we have turned. Now we will establish new connections between Sarajevo and Damascus, Benghazi and Batumi. We will do this peacefully. By respecting borders, we will not go to war with anyone. This is now our strength. Now they are completely different states, but 110 years ago Yemen and Skopje, Batumi and Benghazi were part of the same country, that is, part of the Ottoman Empire. When we talk about this, we ignite the flames of neo-Ottomanism accusations, but why are those who united all of Europe not called neo-Romans?” These words belong to the former head of Turkey's foreign policy office, Ahmet Davutoglu.² Modern Turkey is viewed by the world as a country with a Muslim population that Erdoğan has transformed into a more theocratic political system competing with the Arab Islamic world, even claiming to be a “caliphate.” However, there is a certain ideological dilemma in Turkey's "caliphate." That is, Turkey has recently attempted to join the European Union and remains a member of NATO's western military bloc. More specifically, for Turkey to become a leader of the Islamic world, it must abandon any alliances formed or that may be formed with non-Muslim countries. Otherwise, Turkey's role in leading the Turkic-Muslim world or all Islamic countries becomes a problematic situation.

As noted above, Turkey was protected from communism and the Soviet Union's attack through NATO. However, there is no such threat in the current world political arena. In the 20th century, Turkey actively fought in various military missions alongside NATO and U.S. countries, providing infrastructure and political support against Arab countries, Afghanistan, and Iran. On one hand, Ankara claims to be the center of Islam, while on the other hand, Turkey has always been on the other side of the barricades of Muslim countries.

Turkey has participated in military operations in over ten countries across three continents, including Asia, Africa, and Europe, and continues to do so. The geographical area where these military operations are taking place is broader than the territories of the former Ottoman Empire. The strengthening of Turkish military power in countries such as Syria, Iraq, Libya, Mali, the Central African Republic, Ethiopia, Qatar, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Albania, Sudan, Northern Cyprus, and Azerbaijan indicates that Turkey's military strength is growing, and correspondingly, its geopolitical influence is increasing.³ Islam has been successfully used as a geopolitical weapon by Erdoğan and is an integral part of the new “Neo-Ottomanism” doctrine. A more militant version of Islam is employed to fulfill the

² Turkey propagates “Greater Turan” map stretching from Balkans to China <https://greekcitytimes.com/2021/11/23/turkey-propagates-greater-turan/>

³ The Great Turan: Russia's Concerns about Turkey's Growing Reputation in Caucasus and Central Asia - Politics Today <https://politicstoday.org/the-great-turan-russia-turkey-caucasus-central-asia/>

aggressive tasks of Turkish politics. In countries where Islam is the predominant religion, Turkey is viewed as a liberating country. Erdoğan also successfully utilizes the religious factor to strengthen his power and manipulate domestic politics. His colorful rhetoric clearly demonstrates his approach to instrumentalizing religion. When Erdoğan first stepped into the political arena, he used the following phrases in his speeches: “Mosques are our barracks, their domes are our helmets, minarets are our bayonets, and believers are our soldiers.”⁴ With this factor, Erdoğan sometimes tries to conceal the economic problems and crises arising from the country's strict and partially contradictory foreign policy through religious means. In this sense, the Islamic factor seems to be a unique characteristic for Erdoğan. The propaganda of restoring the Ottoman Empire and creating a “Great Turan” diminishes all of Turkey's internal problems and directs the population's support toward President Erdoğan's foreign policy. Erdoğan has succeeded in reconciling Turkish nationalists (Pan-Turkists) and radical Islamists in Turkey. He synthesized and unified these two movements within the framework of the modern “Neo-Ottomanism” strategy. Under his control, a dangerous alliance for the outside world called the “Grey Wolves Union” was formed with the oversight of his special services and radical religious leaders.⁵ This segment is used very actively by Ankara for political purposes as a reactionary social group.⁶

When Erdoğan officially announced Turkey's expansionist policy, the West watched this policy in silence. The West can only firmly oppose Turkey's expansion towards the European Union member Greece and its excessive interference in European affairs. Russia is trying to establish partnership relations with Turkey in response to Western countries. However, Erdoğan can only be a situational ally for Russia in a short period of time. This is because the geopolitical objectives of Russia and Turkey have historically been contradictory. The main task of Russia's geopolitical minimum towards Turkey is to remove it from NATO. After that, Moscow hopes to turn Turkey from a situational partner into a strategic ally. However, the question arises, “Does Turkey itself, under the leadership of Erdoğan, want this?” Russia needs to act very firmly using any means to achieve this goal. However, for now, Turkey does not want to leave NATO. There is a strong American military infrastructure in Turkey, and 60 military bases and facilities are used for Pentagon interests. Many nuclear weapons are deployed there. Ankara has not yet officially raised the issue of revising or denouncing the international treaty on US-Turkey military cooperation. Meanwhile, the mutual confrontation in the Caucasus region, namely the conflicting dispute between Azerbaijan and Armenia, contradicts Turkey and Russia's interests. The Turkish government's open military and political intervention in the Karabakh conflict to support Azerbaijan has become a dangerous issue for Russia. The escalation of the Karabakh conflict and the results achieved in the form of a trilateral agreement is precisely Turkey's victory. For Turkey, this event is another important step towards creating the “Great Turan.” The official text of the agreement on “ending the war in Karabakh” does not mention Turkish peacekeepers. However, by the decision of the Turkish Grand National Assembly and Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev, a joint peacekeeping mission consisting of Russian and Turkish military personnel has been established. According to the statements of the leaders of Turkey and Azerbaijan, this will be a “new format” for monitoring compliance with the peace. Turkey will work alongside Russia at the Karabakh monitoring center. However, the statements of the Turkish leader regarding the events are of great importance: “We will be alongside the Azerbaijani Armed Forces,

⁴ Turkey propagates “Greater Turan” map stretching from Balkans to China <https://greekcitytimes.com/2021/11/23/turkey-propagates-greater-turan/>

⁵ Grey Wolves: Turkish Ultranationalist Paramilitary or Idealist Hearths? <https://greodynamics.com/grey-wolves-turkish-ultranationalist-paramilitary-or-idealist-hearths/>

⁶ КАКИЕ НЕГАТИВНЫЕ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ МОЖЕТ ИМЕТЬ ИДЕЯ «ВЕЛИКОГО ТУРАНА» ДЛЯ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ? <https://centrasia.institute/kakie-negativnye-posledstviia-mojet-imet-ideia-velikogo-tyrana-dlia-centralnoi-azii.html>

supporting our brothers in accordance with the principle of "one nation, two states."⁷ Here, the emphasis on the phrase "one nation" underscores Turkey's primary goal, which dictates its entire international foreign policy. It is reasonable to assert that Erdoğan aims for expansion beyond the Caucasus. Given the results of the recent military-political events in Karabakh, Turkey has a high likelihood of becoming a new hegemon in the South Caucasus.

Turkey's former Foreign Minister Mevlüt Çavuşoğlu emphasized after the signing of the peace agreement regarding Karabakh: "There are other problems in our region - Georgia, Crimea, Moldova."⁸ The Crimean Peninsula is considered another "conflict zone" between Turkey and Russia. Ankara views itself as responsible for the fate of the Crimean Tatars and actively supports Kyiv. Since 2014, relations between Ankara and Kyiv have strengthened. As a result, Turkey refused to recognize the referendum results. However, the Crimean Peninsula has become part of Russia. Nevertheless, the Crimean Tatar diaspora in Ukraine still plays an important role in establishing Ukraine-Turkey relations. Kyiv purchased nearly fifty Turkish combat drones, which are actively used in the Nagorno-Karabakh region by Azerbaijan. Such contradictions in their mutual relations suggest that Moscow should not have high hopes from Ankara. Russian-Turkish relations can only shift positively based on mutual interests. However, Turkey's overt ambitions towards Central Asia and attempts to exclude Russian and Chinese political circles from this region could lead to a trilateral conflict. In this context, how should Central Asian countries position themselves? After all, they are also countries with their own independent policies. In this situation, all Central Asian countries face a "Security Dilemma." According to this political concept, each country must ensure its own security while not directly or indirectly threatening the security of other countries. Although Central Asian countries gained independence after breaking away from the Soviet Union, they still encounter problems in some areas. The participation of CSTO peacekeeping forces in addressing the unrest in Kazakhstan in January 2020 sparked extensive discussion and conflict in the international political arena. Turkey requested an explanation from the Russian government regarding this situation. Russian diplomats were angered by Turkey's statements about the events in Kazakhstan and its request for clarification from Moscow about the situation there. Russian Foreign Minister Sergey Lavrov requested an explanation from Ankara regarding the statement made by an assistant to the Turkish president concerning the use of CSTO forces in Kazakhstan. Maria Zakharova, the official representative of the Russian Foreign Ministry, commented on Ankara's statement about the situation in Kazakhstan. The assistant to the Turkish president emphasized that all actions were carried out within the framework of Kazakhstan's membership in the organization, viewing Kazakhstan, a former Soviet Republic, as a country that has "freed itself from Soviet oppression."⁹

In this situation, Russia's foreign policy towards Turkey tends to take a negative direction. What kind of foreign policy should Russia pursue regarding Turkey? Modern Russia officially declares itself as a secular, multi-ethnic, and multi-religious state. It has maintained the idea of the "Third Rome" and is attempting to unite all Orthodox-Slavic countries through this ideological framework. If this movement strengthens politically, it could lead to a confrontation between Orthodox-Slavic and Muslim-Turkish countries in international

⁷ «Великий Туран» - самый короткий путь к Хартленду <https://www.geopolitika.ru/article/velikiy-turan-samyu-korotkiy-put-k-hartlendu?ysclid=lywlpntvtl2757530>

⁸ Speech by H.E. Mevlüt Çavuşoğlu, Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Turkey at the Fifth Foreign Ministers' Meeting of the Conference on Interaction and Confidence Building Measures in Asia (CICA), 28 April 2016, Beijing https://www.disisleri.gov.tr/speech-by-h_e_-mevlut-cavusoglu_-minister-of-foreign-affairs

⁹ КАКИЕ НЕГАТИВНЫЕ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ МОЖЕТ ИМЕТЬ ИДЕЯ «ВЕЛИКОГО ТУРАНА» ДЛЯ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ? <https://centrasia.institute/kakie-negativnye-posledstviia-mojet-imet-ideia-velikogo-tyrana-dlia-centralnoi-azii.html>

relations. In such a case, Russia cannot cede the former Soviet territories, particularly Central Asia and Southern Caucasus, which it considers a buffer zone against Turkey.

However, developing such a strategy is challenging due to the fragmented geopolitical integrity of the Russian Federation and the incomplete formation of a national ideology. Russia views itself as the heir to the Byzantine Empire ideologically and religiously and is ready to employ all possible means to preserve this legacy. Additionally, Turkey poses a threat to Russia's national territorial unity by ideologically promoting its own agenda within Russia's internal structures. Erdoğan is establishing a "Turkic World" in the vital interests of Russia. The emergence of a "Great Turan" spanning from the sea to the sea and from the Urals to the Adriatic is not far-fetched.

The concepts of "Pan-Turkism" and "Neo-Ottomanism" illustrate the dynamics of Turkey's foreign policy and the reality of the creation of "Great Turan." The "Great Turan" factor is viewed as the shortest route to "Hartland." According to Brzezinski's universal formula, "Great Turan" would be formed at the expense of Russia, within the ruins of Russia, and in the territory from the Mediterranean Sea to the Laptev Sea. Achieving this goal requires the separation of national autonomies from the Russian Federation and the widespread promotion of Turkish separatism in Russian federal subjects, where Tatars, Bashkirs, Yakuts, and Buryats would transform into "Tatar, Bashkir, Yakut, and Buryat Turks" under the ideology of Pan-Turkism.

Turkey's ideological movement in this direction signifies covert interference in Russia's internal affairs. However, any actions taken towards this goal could significantly disrupt the balance of international relations. Nonetheless, economic relations between Turkey and Russia have not ceased. Ankara derives more economic and financial dividends from its trade relations with Moscow than vice versa. Turkish businesses have a strong presence in the Russian market, particularly in the construction sector, where they hold leading positions. Seventy percent of Turkey's agricultural products are sold in the Russian market, and similarly, 70% of Turkey's tourism business caters to Russian tourists. These economic indicators suggest that the economic-political relationship between Russia and Turkey is unlikely to completely cease in the near future, but neither will it develop positively.

The emergence of such factors and their consequences in the international political arena are concerning not only for Russia but also for other countries. The "Great Turan" factor is not just a problematic situation for Russia; it also poses risks for China and Europe alike.

Given the current situation in international relations, civilizational alliances will emerge against the "Great Turan" alliance. Or, to prevent such potential alliances from forming, "great powers" will try to use all their capabilities to isolate the Muslim-Turkic world. The Muslim-Turkic world cannot achieve any concrete results without forming a military coalition. However, recently, military cooperation relations among the countries that are members of the Turkic States Organization are expanding. For example, on April 4, 2024, a joint statement was adopted at the expanded meeting of the Defense Ministers of Central Asian countries, held in Aktau, Kazakhstan, to conduct military exercises named "Birlestik-2024" in Kazakhstan in July this year. Consequently, these military exercises took place from July 8 to 17 at the "Oymasha" military training ground in Aktau, Kazakhstan. Of course, Tajikistan also participated in these military exercises, even though it is not ethnically Turkic. However, the independent actions of Central Asian countries in the military sphere are noteworthy. From this perspective, as explained by Turkey's ambassador to Azerbaijan, Ismail Alper Joshgun: "It is a valid reason to promote the idea of creating a 'Turkic NATO,' unified under the common Turkic command of the 'Great Turan' army. The level of unifying armed forces within the Turkic States Organization should even surpass that of the North Atlantic

Alliance.¹⁰ In establishing a military alliance, every Turkic country must act collectively. However, Turkmenistan's policy of being a "neutral country" naturally hinders this. If Turkmenistan were to abandon this policy and actively participate in foreign political relations, it would represent a significant move towards the creation of "Great Turan." Today, the possibility of creating and unifying "Great Turan" can be viewed from two perspectives. First, three members of the "Turkic States Organization"—Turkey, Azerbaijan, and Kazakhstan—have favorable opportunities related to maritime trade. Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and Azerbaijan are important strategic countries rich in oil and gas resources. These two factors also indicate the broad economic opportunities available to these countries. Currently, Turkmenistan, which participates as an observer in the meetings of the "Turkic States Organization" and possesses both aforementioned opportunities, could open the door to significant possibilities by joining the organization.

At the same time, another issue is related to how the member countries of the Turkic States Organization will perceive the Turkish government's recognition of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus as an independent country. Following Turkey's military assistance to Azerbaijan regarding the situation in Nagorno-Karabakh, Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev announced his readiness to recognize Northern Cyprus. Moreover, Ilham Aliyev even invited the leader of Northern Cyprus, Ersin Tatar, to make an official visit to Azerbaijan.¹¹ If this decision is accepted by other Turkic countries, it will face resistance from the West. Despite Turkey's determined efforts to join the European Union and being a member of NATO, it aims to fully annex Cyprus. This action would further exacerbate the conflict between the Muslim-Turkic and Catholic-Western spheres. Moreover, Turkey does not limit itself to Cyprus but also attempts to include Greece and other Balkan countries within its sphere of influence. In this effort, Hungary could serve as a supportive country for Turkey. Despite having a different religion and culture, Hungary has consistently sought to improve its relations with Turkic countries. On the other hand, Hungary considers itself a historically Turkic nation. This claim poses a significant threat to Western Europe and the United States, as Hungary is a member of both the European Union and NATO. The potential loss of Hungary would be a considerable defeat for the West. Even if the "Turon factor" does not establish a unified alliance, there could be a formation of some sort of alliance among Turkic countries to stand against their political rivals in international relations. Steps are being taken in a phased manner to achieve this goal. For instance, the announcement of the declaration regarding a common Turkic alphabet, adopted during the third meeting of the Turkic World Common Alphabet Commission held in Baku from September 9 to 11, 2024, serves as an example.¹² Certainly, the Turon Union will not emerge and form quickly; however, the cooperation of all Turkic countries in mutual political engagement is essential and important for the formation of the Union.

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